

Feature Extraction using Conformal Geometric Algebra for AdaBoost Algorithm based In-plane Rotated Face Detection

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Abstract. In this paper, we propose a novel face detection method based on the AdaBoost algorithm. In the past few years, a variety of variant AdaBoost approaches has been proposed and obtained increasing success in both performance and robustness. However, those approaches have not focused much on the geometric characteristics of face images. A new way to apply AdaBoost is introduced in this paper with the utilization of Conformal Geometric Algebra for extracting features from input samples. By analysis and experiments, using Conformal Geometric Algebra, we can find the hyper-spheres (-planes) that mostly fit data points and yield very low error for classification in both frontal and in-plane rotated face detection. Haar-like patterns are used as well but in a more pertinent approach to achieve more informative features. In comparison with the state-of-the-art face detection method developed by Paul Viola and Michael J. Jones, our proposed method can gain approximately the same accuracy as their framework. From a sufficient number of experiments, we prove that a small subset of the feature set can be totally adequate to develop a strong classifier with comparable performance and accuracy. Thus, iterating over the whole set of features to choose the best one for each round of AdaBoost is no longer needed. Besides, the memory usage for training is significantly reduced if we compare with the Viola-Jones system and a large amount of RAM is no longer required to store feature values as in their method.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, face detection is one of the most popular fields which is still developing and applied to a wide range of tasks from industry to daily life.

There have been a variety of approaches and solutions for this problems. Viola and Jones (Viola-Jones) proposed the state-of-the-art method in [18, 19] which

gained success in both performance and robustness. Their method is based on the AdaBoost algorithm which is simple to implement and is efficient to obtain high accuracy. Inspired by their work, a number of methods have been proposed to advance face detection systems.

Stan Z. Li et al. [10] introduced FloatAdaBoost which utilized AdaBoost in a backtrack mechanism, and where errors are minimized directly after each iteration. Real AdaBoost, proposed by Bo Wu et al. [20] for a multi-view face detection framework, estimates the confidence to be a face or a non-face image. Descending from Real AdaBoost, Vector Boosting was invented by Chang Huang et al. [9] for multi-view face detection which applied a pyramid structure and a decision Width-First-Search tree structure. A normalized pixel difference has first been applied as new feature type for face detection in [11] by Shengcai Liao et al., and a deep quadratic tree learner was then used for classification. Takeshi Mita et al. proposed to use joint Haar-like features in [12] which applied co-occurrence of multiple Haar-like features for higher accuracy.

In this paper, we again start from the work of Viola-Jones and propose a new method to apply AdaBoost. There are two main contributions in our approach, they are briefly introduced below and in full detail in the following sections.

First, we utilize Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA) [4, 17, 1, 2, 8, 7] to extract feature values after using Haar-like patterns. The procedure to calculate feature values follows the work of Tuan Pham et al. [13]. To evaluate the performance of our proposed method, we apply CGA with different numbers of Haar-like patterns to construct a feature and the resulting accuracy is then compared to choose the one that works best in practice. The main purpose of the proposed method is to examine the CGA space dimension that is most efficient for the face detection problem. Our algorithm is based on [13] and attempts to search for a hyper-plane (or -sphere) which best separates positive and negative distributions rather than a simple threshold as in the original work.

Second, an integral image representation is utilized more efficiently by using non-integer size patterns. Compared to the original method, we can obtain more informative features that enhance the system performance. We also introduce a simple method which uses lookup tables to quickly find information for a feature and then compute its value in approximately $O(1)$. This contribution is not related to CGA but it helps to enrich the feature pool for the feature selection process. Furthermore, feature values are also non-integer which benefits the training step due to its higher accuracy.

2. Review of Viola-Jones Algorithm

2.1. Haar-like Patterns

Accuracy and robustness are strongly related to how features are extracted and used. In the Viola-Jones method, Haar-like features are applied to find differences of pixel levels within an image region. Examples of Haar-like patterns are shown in Fig. 1.

For each Haar-like pattern, the feature value is the difference between black and white sub-regions as depicted in Fig. 1. By using the integral image technique

Figure 1. Haar-like rectangle patterns used in Viola-Jones system.

proposed by Viola-Jones, the complexity for this task is $O(1)$, which considerably reduces work. Its formula

$$I(x,y) = \sum_{0 \leq x' \leq x, 0 \leq y' \leq y} i(x',y') \quad (2.1)$$

where $i(x,y)$ is the image intensity at pixel (x,y) and $I(x,y)$ is the value of the integral image at pixel (x,y) . Specifically, $I(x,y)$ is sum of the all pixel intensities from position $(0,0)$ to (x,y) .

2.2. AdaBoost Algorithm

Due to the huge number of features related to each image, it is tremendous work to choose the best classifiers from those features. In this context, AdaBoost [15, 16] can be used to select the essential features as well as to train for a strong classifier. This algorithm constructs a strong classifier from a linear combination of weak classifiers with the corresponding weights.

$$F(x) = \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(x), \quad (2.2)$$

where x is an image example, $h_t(x)$ are weak or basic classifiers and each $h_t(x)$ is assigned a weight α_t . Normally, the set $\mathcal{H} = \{h_t(x)\}$ is finite. $F(x)$ is finally compared with half of the sum of all α_t to determine if a sample is positive or negative.

A weak classifier is a function of a feature (f), a threshold (θ) and a polarity (p) that denotes the direction of the inequality

$$h(x, f, p, \theta) = \begin{cases} 1 & p \times f(x) < p \times \theta, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

where θ and p are determined for a particular feature to best classify positive and negative examples. Initially, each training example is equally assigned a weight, and the total weight of positive and negative samples are both equal to 0.5. After p and θ are chosen, in the classification step, an input image will be asserted by the piece-wise function above to obtain the output of that weak classifier. In each round of AdaBoost, the weak classifier that gained the smallest error is chosen and then the weights of the input examples are recalculated to emphasize the wrong classification. The AdaBoost algorithm is fully listed in Alg. 1.

Viola and Jones used AdaBoost and for each weak learner, tried to find the optimal threshold for the classification function. As explained in [15], a weak learner is a procedure of AdaBoost algorithm to find a weak classifier $h_t(x)$ with the lowest training error. Supposing that there are N image examples and K features for each image, they had KN combinations for features and thresholds. In a training round of the AdaBoost procedure, the whole data set needs to be iterated to evaluate the training error for a feature/threshold combination. Thus the complexity of each round to find a weak classifier is $O(NKN)$. By setting the number of weak classifiers to M , the total complexity to train the system is $O(MNKN)$ which is extremely high for real applications.

By sorting the feature values for input images and finding the optimal threshold in linear time, their algorithm can be significantly sped up. The complexity for sorting is $O(N \log_2 N)$ and it takes $O(N)$ to find an optimal threshold, thus the total complexity of this sub-task is $O(\max(N, N \log_2 N)) = O(N \log_2 N)$. Finally, their method's complexity is $O(MKN \log_2 N)$ which is sufficient for training.

Algorithm 1 Original AdaBoost algorithm

Input: input examples $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)$ where y_i is 1 for positive and 0 for negative examples, respectively

Output: final strong classifier

- 1: Initialize input weights for positive and negative examples, respectively

$$w_{1,t} \leftarrow \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2\text{pos}} & \text{if } y_i = 1 \\ \frac{1}{2\text{neg}} & \text{if } y_i = 0 \end{cases}$$

- 2: **for** $t \leftarrow 1, T$ **do**

- 3: Normalize weights $w_{t,i} \leftarrow \frac{w_{t,i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_{t,j}}$

- 4: Select the best weak classifier that minimizes error:

$$\varepsilon_t = \min_{f,p,\theta} \sum_i w_{t,i} |h(x_i, f, p, \theta) - y_i|$$

- 5: Define $h_t(x) = h(x, f_t, p_t, \theta_t)$ where f_t, p_t , and θ_t are the minimizers of ε_t

- 6: Update the weights:

$$w_{t+1,i} = w_{t,i} \beta_t^{1-e_{t,i}}$$

where $e_{t,i} = 0$ if example x_i is classified correctly, $e_{t,i} = 1$ otherwise, and $\beta_t = \frac{\varepsilon_t}{1-\varepsilon_t}$

- 7: **end for**

- 8: Combine final strong classifier

$$C(x) \leftarrow \begin{cases} 1 & \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(x) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Table 1. Color map for Haar-like type (b), white region denoted by 1 otherwise -1 .

1	-1	1
1	-1	1
1	-1	1

3. Proposed Method by Conformal Geometric Algebra

3.1. New Haar-like Value Extraction

In this paper, we propose to use Haar-like rectangles with non-integer size. With this method, we can obtain more informative Haar-like patterns. Thus, in the training procedure, better classifiers can be chosen and yield higher classification rates. Fig. 2 shows an example of our new non integer-sized rectangle. For this example, Table 1 shows a 3×3 Haar-like pattern (type (b) in Fig. 1) applied to a 3×4 sub-window image. The numbers inside each cell indicate the gray levels of pixels.

15	12	15	21
10	5	5	16
12	8	3	6

Figure 2. 3×4 sub-window image with non integer-sized feature

By using the color map described above, feature values can be quickly computed with integer or non-integer size Haar-like patterns. In the example of Fig. 2, the feature value is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 15 + 10 + 12 + \frac{1}{3} \times (12 + 5 + 8) \\
 & - \frac{2}{3} \times (12 + 5 + 8) - \frac{2}{3} \times (15 + 5 + 3) \\
 & + \frac{1}{3} \times (15 + 5 + 3) + 21 + 16 + 6 = 64.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

One of the advances of this paper compared to the classical Viola-Jones method is the lookup table generation. Given a Haar-like type, we can generate the corresponding size and position for it in an input image. By this invention, in the training process, we can immediately get the parameter of a feature and then its value. It is

the reason why feature values for the whole data set for training and testing are not required to be pre-computed, nor is a large amount of RAM required.

To be more specific, Haar-like values for each input image are obtained by applying the color map to Haar-like patterns and the cost for this computation is approximately $O(1)$ so the processing time for this task can be neglected.

3.2. Foundations of Conformal Geometric Algebra

Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA) [4, 17, 1, 2, 8, 7] extends the real Euclidean vector space \mathbb{R}^m by adding two orthonormal basis vectors squaring to $+1$ and -1 , respectively. It results in the space determined by $m+2$ basis vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_m, \mathbf{e}_+, \mathbf{e}_-\}$ and its 2^{m+2} -dimensional conformal Clifford geometric algebra is denoted by $\mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$ and called CGA.

In CGA, a real Euclidean vector $\mathbf{x} = \sum_i^m x_i \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is mapped to a conformal point $P \in \mathbb{R}^{m+1,1} \subset \mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$ by

$$P = \mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0, \quad \mathbf{e}_\infty = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_- - \mathbf{e}_+), \quad \mathbf{e}_0 = \mathbf{e}_- + \mathbf{e}_+. \quad (3.2)$$

The general form of a conformal vector S in $\mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$ for representing hyper-planes and hyper-spheres is

$$S = \mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0, \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathbf{s} = \sum_i^m s_i \mathbf{e}_i$ is a vector in the real Euclidean sub-space \mathbb{R}^m , and s_∞ and s_0 are scalar coefficients.

A hyper-sphere S_p in CGA is defined as

$$S_p = \mathbf{o} + \frac{1}{2} \{\|\mathbf{o}\|^2 - r^2\} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0, \quad (3.4)$$

where $\mathbf{o} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the Euclidean center position vector, and r the scalar radius of the sphere, respectively, with $P \in S_p \Leftrightarrow P \cdot S_p = 0$ for any conformal point P on the sphere S_p .

Similarly, a hyper-plane π can be expressed as a conformal vector in CGA by

$$\pi = \mathbf{n} + d \mathbf{e}_\infty, \quad (3.5)$$

where $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the Euclidean normal vector, and $X \in \pi \Leftrightarrow X \cdot \pi = 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{x} + d = 0$ in real space \mathbb{R}^m for a point X on the plane, and d the oriented scalar distance from the origin to the plane.

3.3. Application of Conformal Geometric Algebra

Viola-Jones only used one Haar-like feature for each weak classifier in each round, the whole set of features is compared to choose the best one which achieves the lowest error. However, there is still room to further improve and benefit even more from Haar-like features and the power of AdaBoost.

In most of the recent research on face detection with AdaBoost using Haar-like patterns as features, the features have not been efficiently mined because the main purpose is just to obtain the smallest error without analyzing the data representation itself. Thus, in this paper, we propose to apply CGA to face detection. The key point in our method is to figure out the best hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) that fits all feature values calculated from input images. For this task, we use results from [13]

and we propose a new method to estimate a hyper-sphere or hyper-plane that best fits to a set of points by using CGA.

Mathematically, we assume a set of n points $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_k = \sum_i^m x_{k,i} \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m, k = 1, \dots, n\}$. By transforming each Euclidean point to a point in CGA, we obtain in $\mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$ the equivalent set

$$\mathcal{P} = \{P_k = \mathbf{x}_k + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0, k = 1, \dots, n\}. \quad (3.6)$$

This set of points \mathcal{P} is approximated to fit the hyper-sphere (or -plane) represented by the conformal vector $S = \mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0$ in $\mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$. The problem is solved by minimizing the error function E defined as

$$E = \sum_{k=1}^n d^2(P_k, S) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\mathbf{x}_k \cdot \mathbf{s} - s_\infty - \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 s_0 \right)^2, \quad (3.7)$$

where $d(P, S)$ is a distance measure between point P and hyper-sphere (or -plane) S . It means the position of P with respect to S , and in particular it vanishes if and only if P lies on S . It is given by the inner product of P and S

$$\begin{aligned} d(P, S) &\propto P \cdot S \\ &= \left(\mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0 \right) \cdot (\mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0) \\ &= \mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{s} - s_\infty - \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 s_0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

By restricting to $\|\mathbf{s}\|^2 = 1$ and adding a non-negative Lagrange multiplier λ , the problem becomes the optimization of

$$L = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\mathbf{x}_k \cdot \mathbf{s} - s_\infty - \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 s_0 \right)^2 - \lambda (\|\mathbf{s}\|^2 - 1). \quad (3.9)$$

The solution to this problem has clearly been proven and explained in [13] (see also [3]) by using the eigen-decomposition for

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{s} = \lambda \mathbf{s}. \quad (3.10)$$

In this context, an eigen-vector \mathbf{s} is used to represent the hyper-sphere (-plane) $S = \mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0$, that fits the input point set, and the eigen-value λ is the variance or the sum of the squared distances between P_k and S . The multivector \mathbf{A} is defined by

$$\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) \mathbf{f}^T \mathbf{x}_k, \quad (3.11)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{f}_\infty - \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{f}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m, \\ \mathbf{f}_\infty &= \frac{-\sum_4 \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{x}_k + \sum_2 \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \mathbf{x}_k}{(\sum_2)^2 - n \sum_4}, \\ \mathbf{f}_0 &= \frac{\sum_2 \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{x}_k - n \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \mathbf{x}_k}{(\sum_2)^2 - n \sum_4}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

with the extra parameters: sum of squares $\sum_2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2$, and sum of the fourth powers $\sum_4 = \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^4$. The coefficients s_∞ and s_0 can be calculated from the vectors \mathbf{f}_∞ and \mathbf{f}_0 as

$$s_\infty = \mathbf{f}_\infty \cdot \mathbf{s}, \quad \frac{1}{2}s_0 = \mathbf{f}_0 \cdot \mathbf{s}. \quad (3.13)$$

3.4. Apply Conformal Geometric Algebra to AdaBoost

To apply to AdaBoost, instead of using only one Haar-like feature as in the Viola-Jones system, we combine two Haar-like values to construct a point \mathbf{x}_k for every input example. In this approach we have the set of input examples used for training is $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_k = \sum_i^m x_{k,i} \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m\}$, $m = 2$, and the Boolean variable $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$, for non-face and face examples (indicated with index $c \in \{0, 1\}$ below), respectively.

For each subset of face and non-face examples, a hyper-sphere (or -plane) should be estimated using the formulas in [13]. After solving for eigen-vector and eigen-value \mathbf{s}_0 , λ_0 for the non-face cluster, and \mathbf{s}_1 , λ_1 for the face cluster, respectively, probabilities that an input example happens to be in each cluster are calculated according to the following probability formulas that are fully specified in [13].

The density function that a point \mathbf{x} belongs to any of the hyper-sphere (-plane) clusters is denoted by $S_{c,l} = \mathbf{s}_{c,l} + s_{\infty c,l} \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_{0c,l} \mathbf{e}_0$, $l \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with eigen-values $\lambda_{c,l}$ given by

$$\Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,l}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\lambda_{c,l}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d^2(X, S_{c,l})}{2\lambda_{c,l}}\right). \quad (3.14)$$

In our system, $m = 2$, due to the use of two Haar-like patterns for each example and $c \in \{0, 1\}$, for non-face ($c = 0$) and face ($c = 1$) clusters, respectively. The posterior probability density function for \mathbf{x} , given the cluster $y = c$, is

$$\Pr(\mathbf{x} | c) = \prod_l^m \Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,l}). \quad (3.15)$$

This posterior probability is used for the classification process, by comparing the probability that an example belongs to each cluster

$$h(\mathbf{x}, S_0, \lambda_0, S_1, \lambda_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & \Pr(\mathbf{x} | 1) > \Pr(\mathbf{x} | 0), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.16)$$

Our proposed method is clearly shown in the following Alg. 2. CGA eigen-values and eigen-vectors are computed using Alg. 3. The best single feature for CGA of a one-dimensional (1-D) space is found by applying Alg. 4.

Algorithm 2 AdaBoost with proposed CGA method

Input: input examples $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)$ where y_i is 1 for positive and 0 for negative examples, respectively

Output: final strong classifier

- 1: Initialize input weights for positive and negative examples, respectively

$$w_{1,i} \leftarrow \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2^{\text{pos}}} & \text{if } y_i = 1 \\ \frac{1}{2^{\text{neg}}} & \text{if } y_i = 0 \end{cases}$$

- 2: **for** $t \leftarrow 1, T$ **do**

- 3: Normalize weights: $w_{t,i} \leftarrow \frac{w_{t,i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_{t,j}}$

- 4: **for** $i \leftarrow 1, m - 1$ **do**

- 5: Apply Alg. 4 to find one best single feature

- 6: **end for**

- 7: Construct $(m - 1)$ -dimensional \mathbf{x} from $m - 1$ best single features

- 8: Randomly select K' features from full set of features

- 9: **for** each of K' features **do**

- 10: Compute feature values for every example to construct \mathbf{x} in m dimensions

- 11: Apply Alg. 3 to find eigen-values λ_0, λ_1 and eigen vectors $\mathbf{s}_0, \mathbf{s}_1$

- 12: Define conformal vectors for the hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) S of non-face (index 0) and face (index 1) regions:

$$S_0 = \mathbf{s}_0 + s_{\infty;0} \mathbf{e}_{\infty} + s_{0;0} \mathbf{e}_0, \quad S_1 = \mathbf{s}_1 + s_{\infty;1} \mathbf{e}_{\infty} + s_{0;1} \mathbf{e}_0$$

- 13: Compute the posterior probability for each \mathbf{x} to be in a face and non-face region:

$$\Pr(\mathbf{x} | c) = \prod_l^m \Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,l})$$

where $c \in \{0, 1\}$ for non-face and face respectively

- 14: Select the best weak classifier that minimizes error:

$$\varepsilon_t = \min_{\mathbf{x}, S_0, \lambda_0, S_1, \lambda_1} \sum_i w_{t,i} |h(\mathbf{x}, S_0, \lambda_0, S_1, \lambda_1) - y_i|$$

- 15: Define $h_t(\mathbf{x}) = h(\mathbf{x}, S'_0, \lambda'_0, S'_1, \lambda'_1)$ where $S'_0, \lambda'_0, S'_1, \lambda'_1$ are minimizers of ε_t

- 16: Calculate $\alpha_t \leftarrow \ln\left(\frac{1-\varepsilon_t}{\varepsilon_t}\right)$

- 17: **end for**

- 18: Update weights: $w_{t+1,i} \leftarrow w_{t,i} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_t}\right)^{1-e_{t,i}}$ where $e_{t,i} = 0$ if correct, otherwise 1

- 19: **end for**

- 20: Combine final strong classifier $C(x) \leftarrow \begin{cases} 1 & \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(x) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Algorithm 3 Compute eigen values and conformal eigen vectors

Input: set of points $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_k = \sum_i^n x_{k,i} e_i \in \mathbb{R}^m, k = 1, \dots, n\}$ **Output:** eigen-value λ and conformal eigen vector \mathbf{s}

- 1: Compute Σ_2 and Σ_4
 - 2: Compute \mathbf{f}_∞ and \mathbf{f}_0
 - 3: Compute $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$: $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{f}_\infty - \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{f}_0$
 - 4: Construct matrix $\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k))^T$
 - 5: Solve eigen decomposition problem: $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} = \lambda \mathbf{s}$
 - 6: Compute parameters s_∞ and s_0 : $s_\infty = \mathbf{f}_\infty \cdot \mathbf{s}$, $\frac{1}{2} s_0 = \mathbf{f}_0 \cdot \mathbf{s}$
-

Algorithm 4 Select best single feature for 1-D CGA

Input: input examples $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)$ where y_i is 1 for positive and 0 for negative examples, respectively**Output:** best single feature

- 1: Randomly select K' features from full set of features
- 2: **for** each of the K' features **do**
- 3: Compute feature values for every example to construct a 1-dimensional \mathbf{x}
- 4: Apply Alg. 3 to find eigen-values λ_0, λ_1 and eigen vectors $\mathbf{s}_0, \mathbf{s}_1$
- 5: Define conformal vectors for the hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) for face (index 1) and non-face (index 0) regions:

$$S_0 = \mathbf{s}_0 + s_{\infty;0} \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_{0;0} \mathbf{e}_0, \quad S_1 = \mathbf{s}_1 + s_{\infty;1} \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_{0;1} \mathbf{e}_0$$

- 6: Compute the posterior probability for each \mathbf{x} to be in a face and non-face region:

$$\Pr(\mathbf{x} | c) = \Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,0})$$

where $c \in \{0, 1\}$ for non-face and face respectively

- 7: Select the feature that minimizes error:

$$\varepsilon = \min_{\mathbf{x}, S_0, \lambda_0, S_1, \lambda_1} \sum_i w_{t,i} |h(\mathbf{x}, S_0, \lambda_0, S_1, \lambda_1) - y_i|$$

- 8: **end for**
-

4. Experiments and Results

4.1. Experiments

In training and testing processes, we use the data set Yi-Qing [21] from an analysis of the Viola-Jones system which consists of 24×24 gray scale PNG images. Since the border region does not support choosing the best Haar-like pattern for each image, we crop every input image to 18×18 . The number of Haar-like patterns for each category in Fig. 1 are now: 23409, 18496, 23409, 18496 and 23409, for (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e), respectively.

Because the input images in the data set come with different qualities of brightness and contrast, we first normalize [14] those images for both training and testing

Figure 3. Original Yi-Qing data set images before normalization

Figure 4. Yi-Qing data set images after normalization.

processes. Samples of images before and after the normalization process are listed in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

We conduct two kinds of training that are for frontal faces and in-plane rotated faces. Rotated face images are generated by rotating original frontal faces in [21] with angles varied from -60° to 60° . Examples of in-plane rotated faces are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. In-plane rotated face images from Yi-Qing data set.

Table 2. Number of face/non-face images in Yi-Qing data set.

	Training set	Testing set
Face	2000	2916
Non-face	2000	5960
Total	4000	7960

Tab. 2 shows the number of face/non-face input examples we used in the training and testing process in both kinds of detection. Our system has been implemented totally from scratch in Java. We trained and tested this system on a Mac OS with 8 GB 1600MHz DDR3 of memory and a 2.6 GHz Intel Core i5 processor.

Besides comparing with the Viola-Jones system, we apply CGA in different ways by varying the number of Haar-like patterns from one to three, that make up a CGA point \mathbf{x} . In the implementation that utilizes multiple Haar-like features, we need to choose the best $m - 1$ single Haar-like features as in Alg. 4, then the last feature is chosen to construct a point \mathbf{x} that has m dimensions. To be more

specific, the best $m - 1$ single Haar-like features are chosen by applying CGA with one dimension and the last one is found by CGA in m dimension by combining with the other $m - 1$ best single Haar-like patterns already obtained.

4.2. Results

Fig. 6 shows the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) for our proposed method and that of Viola-Jones with the frontal face data set. Three versions of CGA are involved in this experiment. As shown in the figure, our system with CGA achieves higher curves that denote better classification rates compared to the Viola-Jones method.

Figure 6. ROC for frontal face detection.

The ROC for the in-plane rotated face dataset for all methods are shown in Fig. 7. Again, our proposed method using CGA gains much better accuracy than the Viola-Jones method. Furthermore, CGA methods which apply two and three combinations of Haar-like patterns (CGA-2 and CGA-3) yield much better performance than when using only one pattern (CGA-1).

Figs. 6 and 7 show that the proposed method outperforms the original Viola-Jones algorithm especially in the in-plane rotated face dataset. Because in-plane rotated faces are distributed over a hyper-sphere (or hyper-plane) in high dimensional space, the proposed method using 2-D or 3-D CGA density functions performs better than only using the previous threshold method or a 1-D CGA density function.

Figs. 8 and 9 show the error rate versus the change in number of weak classifiers for each method. It is clearly seen that our proposed method has lower error

Figure 7. ROC for in-plane rotated face detection.

than the original Viola-Jones method, showing that to obtain given error rates, fewer weak classifiers are required by our CGA method.

In the Viola-Jones system, each round of AdaBoost is trained with the whole set of features to choose the best weak classifier. By experiments, we also illustrated that it is furthermore sufficient to choose good weak classifiers and combine them to a strong classifier by randomly choosing a small number of features. After conducting several experiments, $K' = 5000$ was observed to be adequate for a comparable level of precision and also reduced the training time.

Our proposed method using CGA achieves higher accuracy than the Viola-Jones approach due to the effectiveness of exploiting geometric characteristics of the face and non-face distributions. The key idea of previous algorithms applying the Viola-Jones method is finding the optimal threshold that best separates two distributions. However, this method was found to be inefficient when these two distributions overlap which leads to a high level of error for the classification.

To overcome this difficulty, $m = 2$ or higher dimensional Conformal Geometric Algebra is applied to find the hyper-sphere (or -plane) that best fits face and non-face regions rather than using a simple threshold that can not sufficiently discriminate the geometry of the distributions.

Fig. 10 denotes the histogram for feature values computed from the first weak classifier when we apply the Viola-Jones method to the frontal face data set. From the figure, it is clearly seen that the best threshold can still yield a high value of error due to the large overlap between the two regions. In contrast, if we apply our new CGA algorithm, we can gain a much lower error value after the first round

Figure 8. Error rate versus number of weak classifiers with frontal face detection.

Figure 9. Error rate versus number of weak classifiers with in-plane rotated face detection.

of AdaBoost. Furthermore, the higher the dimension of the CGA, the better face and non-face distributions can be separated. Fig. 11 plots the density function of CGA for the first weak classifier in 1-D CGA. Figs. 12 and 13 show that by using 2-D CGA, the two regions for face and non-face images appear well separated and this results in a very low error rate. This is the reason why our proposed method is superior to the original Viola-Jones method. In Fig. 11, the x -axis is the feature value and the y -axis denotes the CGA density function. And in Fig. 12, x -axis and y -axis denote the feature values that make up a CGA point \mathbf{x} and the z -axis is the CGA density function.

Figure 10. Histogram of feature values from 1st weak classifier by Viola-Jones method.

Figure 11. 1-D CGA density function from 1st weak classifier.

Figure 12. 2-D CGA density function from 1st weak classifier.

Figure 13. Contour for 2-D CGA density function from 1st weak classifier.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we propose a novel approach to the face detection problem by applying Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA). Our method achieves as high as or even higher accuracy than the Viola-Jones algorithm. The proposed method of frontal and in-plane rotated face detection using 2-D or 3-D CGA density functions was better than only using a simple threshold or a 1-D CGA density function.

Furthermore, the integral image technique has been improved in this paper, and results in enhancement on feature mining for training weak classifiers and the detection accuracy became therefore higher as well.

We also verified that a small set of randomly selected features is enough for developing a strong classifier with similar detection rate. By using this realization, the training time is significantly reduced as well as substantially improving system performance.

For future work, the present research may be extended and improved by applying Haar *wavelets*¹ for constructing a point \mathbf{x} . For each image, we can repeatedly calculate a feature value by utilizing a Haar-like pattern, then the image can be rescaled by a predefined scaling factor and one can find the corresponding feature value again with the same Haar-like pattern. Finally, all the computed feature values can be combined to form a point \mathbf{x} , then followed by the AdaBoost algorithm as explained in this paper. The purpose of this technique would be to preserve the main characteristics of any input image after applying a Haar-like pattern while simultaneously removing unnecessary or noisy information from the image. We therefore

¹Wavelets in Clifford geometric algebra have previously been studied, e.g., in [6].

expect that it will be more advanced and sensitive than only using several random Haar-like patterns for a point \mathbf{x} .

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